

Technology of Forming the Image of an Educational Institution

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Abstract: *This article examines the problem of forming the image of universities. The concept of "Image" was analyzed, considered through the prism of educational services. The features of forming the image of an educational service, as well as the main elements of the image of a university were considered. The technology of forming the image of an educational institution is considered.*

Keywords: *higher education, image, technology, competitiveness, applicant.*

Introduction. For each organization, it is necessary to carry out targeted work on forming its own image. The need to form the image of an educational institution is determined by the following reasons (according to Sukhareva O.):

- firstly, competition among educational institutions of one territory in the struggle for the recruitment of students and the retention of the contingent;
- secondly, a strong positive image facilitates the access of an educational institution to the best possible resources: financial, informational, human, etc.;
- thirdly, having a formed positive image, an educational institution, all other things being equal, becomes more attractive to teachers, since it appears to be capable of providing stability and social protection, job satisfaction and professional development to a greater extent;
- fourthly, a stable positive image gives the effect of acquiring a certain strength by the educational institution - in the sense that it creates a reserve of trust in everything that happens within the walls of the institution, including innovative processes [1].

Main part. The formation of an image is the first step in building a good school. And the initiative here should come exclusively from the educational institution itself [2].

L. Yu. Shemyatikhina notes that the formation and development of the image space of an educational institution involves the implementation of stages:

- Stage 1 - internal image assessment - the institution's staff conducts a subjective assessment of the image, assigning points from 1 to 9 for each component, then the average score is calculated and the rating of each of the components is determined;
- Stage 2 - external image assessment - is carried out on the basis of an analysis of the opinions of consumers of educational services, partners, experts (questionnaires, expert assessments, analysis of publications in the press);
- Stage 3 – implementation of communication impacts on target groups to form and consolidate the image space of the educational institution;

- Stage 4 – image assessment after a certain period of time to compare indicators, make adjustments to the work.

Formation of an image is a process during which a certain planned image is created based on the available resources. But how can we understand which image is most preferable for the “right” target audience? And how can we determine the volume and specificity of our resources? It often happens that managers do not even suspect how many opportunities there are in a school for creating its positive image. Moreover, the solution to this problem can significantly enrich the pedagogical process itself, it is only a matter of the correct distribution of common efforts.

Let us highlight the main stages of image formation.

Stage I - defining the mission.

You need to start with an analysis of the external environment. The pedagogical specificity of the institution dictates its own laws, therefore, first you need to decide on the basic idea of the educational institution. It can also be called a "concept", "mission", "highlight", etc. The result of this stage should be a clear understanding of what your strengths and weaknesses are. The further strategy here is simple: we actualize and popularize the strengths, and work with the problems.

Stage II — defining the target audience.

When planning image work, it is necessary to understand what target audience you would like to attract as allies. These may be: students, parents, the staff of the educational institution, social partners, the media.

- Students. Undoubtedly, school graduates are almost the main "PR people" of the educational institution. The memory of the school is stored for a long time, and if the image that the children have formed upon graduation is attractive, they will definitely bring their children to this school. In addition, it is the students, while still studying at school, who serve as its kind of "calling card": what they talk about their school days (especially on the Internet), or how they behave in public places directly demonstrates certain standards accepted in the school community.
- Parents of students. These are the most authoritative subjects, capable not only of assessing the work of the school, but also of correcting public opinion and the opinion of their children about it. That is why parents are the main target group that must be focused on in image work.
- Social partners (real and potential). Today, social activities are increasingly important for successful promotion in the market. But it is unlikely that any organization that needs to acquire a positive image will invest money in vague school projects. As a rule, they help only those who have a good reputation and high social and public activity - after all, the benefits of such a partnership should be mutual.
- Mass media. The media are a kind of intermediary between the school and society. Thanks to timely information about the plans or achievements of the educational institution, you can significantly expand the circle of your potential partners and (or) form a positive opinion of yourself in the eyes of others.

Stage III - planning.

At this stage, specific events related to image formation are developed. They can be conditionally divided into internal and external.

Internal: improving the organizational (corporate) culture. This may include the creation of school symbols, development of a dress code (clothing standards), changing the quality of relationships between all participants in the educational process, teaching business ethics, etc.

It is important to remember that the openness and democracy of the school directly depends on how attractive what you are going to "open" to others looks.

External: broadcasting the goals and activities of the school to external "consumers" - parents, social partners, the media. This is the creation and regular replenishment of the school website, promotions, written and oral contacts, including information through booklets, memos, leaflets, sending out letters of thanks, participation in large-scale projects, research, volunteer activities - that is, in all events that have a wide public resonance.

The result of this stage should be the role distribution of the load. The most important thing here is that the image-building activity affects the interests and efforts of all members of the school community. Of no small importance at the planning stage is the issue of the nature of feedback (or monitoring).

Stage IV — implementation of planned activities.

The most important thing in the implementation of any activities to form the image of an educational organization is their organic integration into the educational process.

Stage V — effectiveness check.

At this stage (usually annually), an analysis of the compliance of the obtained image with the desired result is carried out. A mandatory condition here is the dissemination of the monitoring results to all participants in such activities. By the way, the very interest of an educational institution in gaining a good reputation makes a pleasant impression on others.

Conclusion. Schematically, the mechanism for forming the image of an educational institution can be represented as follows.

Figure 1. Stages of forming the image of an educational organization.

Thus, the final result, i.e. the goal of image formation, is to increase the competitiveness of the educational institution.

Thus, the construction of the image of an educational institution - as an emotionally charged image of a school, often consciously formed, possessing purposefully set characteristics and designed to exert a psychological influence of a certain direction on specific groups of society

List of references

1. Sukhoreva, O. Image of educational institutions / O. Sukhareva // Nar. education. - 2009. - No. 10. - P. 135 - 139.
2. Shepel, V.M. Imageology. How to please people [Text] / V.M. Shepel - M.: Public education, 2002. - 345 p.
3. Kashcheev, I. Marketing aspects of forming the image of the enterprise in modern conditions / I. Kashcheev // Entrepreneurship. - 2012. - No. 1. - P. 107.
4. Shkardun V.D., Akhtyamovym T.V. Assessment and formation of the corporate image of the enterprise // Marketing in Russia and abroad. 2012. No. 3. P. 72.
5. Nuriddinova, M. N., & Zokirovich, S. A. (2022). FEATURES OF WORLD RANKINGS OF UNIVERSITIES. *World Bulletin of Management and Law*, 10, 95-98.
6. Zakirjanovna, Y. M., Nuriddinova, M. N., & Qizi, C. B. U. (2022). Higher education in the era of digitalization.
7. Mukumova, N. N., & Olimova, L. E. (2020). Market of Higher Education Services in Uzbekistan. *Journal of marketing and Emerging Economics*.
8. Мукумова, Н. Н. (2021). Высшее образование в эпоху цифровизации. *Наука, техника и образование*, (6 (81)), 54-57.
9. Мукумова, Н. Н., & Олимова, Л. Э. (2021). СТАНОВЛЕНИЕ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО РЫНКА ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УСЛУГ. *Вестник науки и образования*, (15-1 (118)), 21-24.